

Parallel and hierarchically-distributed Shoreline Alert Model (SAM)

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Abstract—In this paper, the Shoreline Alert Model (SAM) is presented as a component of a computation platform based on workflows dedicated to extreme weather/marine event simulation. The model aims to mitigate the effects of global change by providing decision-makers, scientists, and engineers with a novel, next-generation tool set for facing extreme weather events and implementing related management or emergency responses. SAM uses a parallelization schema, allowing users to run it on heterogeneous parallel architectures. As a result, SAM produces approximately 24 times faster results than the baseline when using shared memory with distributed memory and dealing with about 20,000 transects along the Campania coastline. The system is based on the algorithms of the open-source numerical models WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting) and WW3 (Wavewatch III) implemented with refraction and shoaling routines together with run-up equations to form the modeling chain use for coastal flooding assessment.

Index Terms—Marine ingression, parallel environmental modeling, hierarchical distributed computation, coastal flooding.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Coastal areas are becoming more vulnerable to extreme weather events due to population pressure and climate change effects such as sea level rise and storm patterns [1]. This risk affects sandy coastal systems and high coast systems, which suffer damage due to increasingly intense and frequent phenomena [2], [3]. Sea storms are events caused by atmospheric pressure conditions, and storm surges are sudden shifts in water masses. Climate change is putting a strain on coastal systems, and the development of Early Warning Systems (EWS) is necessary to prevent damage and loss of life. Mathematical models provide validated and consistent information on changing water levels as output is monitored with appropriate alarm thresholds. The development and implementation of EWS are becoming more and more necessary to overcome the difficulties and timelines for coastal defense works, as they enable timely measures to be taken before flood waters arrive. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [4] addresses early warning and gives it an essential role across

the Sustainable Development Goals. High-performance computing is critical in developing early warning systems for shoreline coastlines and can help decision-makers respond more quickly and effectively to potential disasters. EWS then enhances the prevention and preparedness activities that mitigate the effects of disasters on lives, property, and the environment [5]. High-Performance Computing can enable the development of more sophisticated early warning systems. For example, HPC can be used to develop models combining sensing, monitoring, and decision support components, allowing for more comprehensive and accurate coastal flooding predictions. Furthermore, HPC can integrate data from multiple sources, such as weather forecasts, sea level measurements, and tide gauges. As a result, it can provide a more detailed understanding of potential coastal hazards and enable more effective decision-making.

II. RELATED WORK

Early Warning Systems (EWSs) are often used to mitigate the destructive consequences for coastal communities' safety, properties, and infrastructures. They usually need sea state data (i.e., wave characteristics and sea level) offshore the study area as input and output the alert level of imminent coastal flood in the coastal urban area. Merrifield et al. [6] developed an EWS for the shoreline of Imperial Beach (San Diego, Calif) that provides the total water level by combining predictions of tides and sea-level anomalies with wave run-up estimates. In addition, they stated that real-time simulations could be incorporated into the EWS to reduce errors in the forecasts. Recently, Biolchi et al. [7] described the semi-probabilistic XBeach-based coastal EWS system currently used as a Decision Supporting System (DSS) by regional authorities on the decision-making process involving the Emilia Romagna region (Northwest Adriatic Sea, Italy). Following the methodology described in Harley et al. [8], the system calculated maximum water levels for each time step and checked the results against predefined thresholds. Thresholds are parametrized by coastal characterization from natural and urbanized shores to evaluate the storm surge indicators.

III. METHODOLOGY

The EWS has been configured using a high-performance computing system to manage and run a scientific workflow [9]. Workflow components are the community Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) [10], and the Wavewatch III (WW3) [11] numerical models. The workflow starts with the WRF numerical model to forecast the atmospheric forcing needed to fuel the WW3 model for estimating the offshore wave, which drives the initial and boundary conditions for modeling waves in shallow water. The action of waves on the shoreline is affected by offshore sea conditions and variations in bathymetry and angle of approach, which can cause shoaling and refraction. Next, a mathematical equation solver calculates wave features for each coastal profile, while a wave decay submodel is used to assess the run-up height and overtopping discharge. Finally, results are used in an alert system triggered by the forecasted duration and intensity of storm events, considering the area's geomorphology and presence of protection structures.

A. Weather Forecasting Model

The weather forecasting model used WRF, an atmospheric numerical model that computes the 10 m wind fields and other atmospheric forcing needed to drive the WW3 offshore wave model, which in turn yields the initial and boundary conditions for the shallow-water wave simulation of wave transformation and run-up.

B. Wave Forecasting Model

The wave forecasting model is based on wave simulations using the WW3 model, a third-generation wave model developed at NOAA/NCEP. Following the operative procedure described in Di Luccio et al. [12], the WW3 grid point (belonging to the high-resolution d03WW3 spatial domain) nearest to the studied cross-shore profiles is the considered virtual buoy (VB). The focus of this paper is the Shoreline Alert Model (SAM), implementing the empirical approach to evaluate the alert level as a function of the shoreline characteristics implemented using the Python programming language.

C. Shoreline Alert Model

SAM is a numerical solver used in coastal flooding contexts to simulate the run-up height and consequent coastal flooding. The numerical simulations have been implemented on a onedimensional base using Python software designed to be highly modular as a part of the operational forecasting system. SAM output can manage alarm thresholds according to the duration and intensity of the forecasted storm event.

The wave condition in the VB (H_s , T_m and D_m), the beach slope β , the beach width w derived from the cross-shore beach profile, and the bottom depth d represent the main SAM inputs. SAM is designed to be modular concerning the empirical procedure to evaluate the alert level. On the bases of the β value, each coastal profile is associated with a shoreline typology: i) rock-armored structures with narrow surf zones (slope ranging from 1:8 to 1:1); ii) beach (slope up to 1:10); iii) structures located in the surf zone (slope up to 1:1); iv) vertical walls (slope higher than 1:1). For all these scenarios, the evaluation of the wave conditions in shallow water is obtained by the ones given by the WW3 system in VB applying the shoaling and refraction

coefficients as a function of bathymetry and wave angle of approach [13]. The relative coefficients K_s and K_r are given by:

$$K_s = \left(\frac{C_{g_o}}{C_g} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left[\frac{2 \cos^2 kd}{2kd + \sinh 2kd} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

Where C_{g_o} is the celerity in deep water and C_g is the celerity in intermediate water, and k is the wave number.

$$K_r = \left(\frac{b_0}{b} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left[\frac{1 - \sin^2 \alpha_0 \tanh^2 kd}{\cos^2 \alpha_0} \right]^{-\frac{1}{4}} \quad (2)$$

Where b_0/b is the ratio of the distance between two adjacent wave rays on deep and intermediate water and α_0 is the deep water incidence angle. Finally, the incidence angle on depth d is found from Snell's law. Solving for α yields:

$$\alpha = \arcsin \left(\frac{C}{C_0} \sin \alpha_0 \right) \quad (3)$$

So the wave height at a depth d can be determined from the VB wave height through the following equation:

$$H_{s_i} = K_s K_r H_s \quad (4)$$

In the surf zone, the rise of the mean water level at mean depth d was calculated as following Dean et al. [14], where the parameter ζ_b is the wave set down at the breaking depth, given by:

$$\zeta_b = -\frac{1}{16} \gamma_b H_b \quad (5)$$

where H_b is breaking wave height and γ_b is the breaker index.

Various Authors calculated the breaking index. According to [15], the significant breaking index is given by:

$$\gamma_b = 0.56 e^{3.5m} \quad (6)$$

where m is the slope of the seabed.

The barometric setup was calculated as follows:

$$\Delta \zeta = \frac{\Delta P_a}{\rho g} \quad (7)$$

where ΔP_a is the pressure variation during the event.

The run-up height $Ru_{x\%}$ is defined as the wave run-up level, measured vertically from the still water line, which is exceeded by $x\%$ of the number of incident waves [16]. Stockton et al. [17] considered the run-up $Ru_{2\%}$ as a function of two separate terms to consider the different contributions of the wave setup and swash (the latter term on the left-hand side)

$$Ru_{2\%} = 1.1 \left(0.35 \tan \beta (H_0 L_0)^{0.5} + \frac{[H_0 L_0 (0.563 \tan^2 \beta + 0.004)]^{0.5}}{2} \right) \quad (8)$$

H_0 is the deep water significant wave height, which can be related to the value at the VB through the ratio of the respective wave celerity $C_0 = L_0/T_m$ and $C_{VB} = L_{VB}/T_m$ [18]:

$$H_0 = H_s \frac{C_{VB}}{C_0} \quad (9)$$

In VB, the wavelength is equal to $L_{VB} = (2\pi)/k$ in which k is the wave-number obtained by the Hunt approximation of the standard dispersion relation:

$$(kd)^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma^2 d}{g}\right)^2 + \frac{\left(\frac{\sigma^2 d}{g}\right)}{1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} d_n \left(\frac{\sigma^2 d}{g}\right)^n} \quad (10)$$

where d_n are six constant values given by Fenton et al. [19], and σ is the wave frequency.

The wind set up in the coastal sketches where the total effect was high, according to the following equations, Reeve et al. [20]. The contribution of the run-up and the coastal setup, calculated as the sum of wind, wave, and barometric setup, give the input to the coastal flooding evaluation.

IV. SAM MODEL: CROSS-SHORE PROFILES DEFINITION

Transect layout for coastal hazards analysis and subsequent floodplain delineation is determined by physical factors such as changes in topography, bathymetry, shoreline orientation, and land cover data, in addition to societal factors such as variations in development and density. So, to create our transects, we need three fundamental files:

(i) Shape file of coastline; (ii) Digital elevation model (DEM): a digital representation of terrain elevation data; [21] (iii) WaveWatch III re-gridded on DEM domain;

To create transects along the Campania coastline, we first ensure that each point in the shapefile is within the desired area of interest. We then calculate the distance between the current point and the previous one. If this distance exceeds a certain threshold, we divide the segment between the two points into multiple equispaced segments. For each point in the new segment, we calculate the *bearing* between the point and the previous one to create the transect. To create the *sea* profile, we move towards the sea until we encounter a valid value from the WW3 model. To create the *land* profile, we move towards the land until we reach a specific set altitude or distance.

V. SAM MODEL: ARCHITECTURE AND PARALLELIZATION SCHEME.

Fig. 1: SAM hierarchical parallelization schema. np is the number of processors, nt is the number of threads per process.

The proposed parallelization scheme (fig. 1) is based on different parallel sub-schemes that can be combined to provide a *hierarchical parallelization scheme*. The standard paradigm of High-Performance Computing, domain decomposition, is used to divide the problem size (number of transects) into smaller lots and distribute them to several executors, which are instances of a computer program that compute the partition of the problem. Each executor can then decompose its part of the problem to

multiple computing cores running concurrently (threads), increasing overall computing performance as the problem size increases. The communication between processes is done by exchanging data messages. In detail, considering a shared and distributed memory scenario, np represents the number of available processors, and nt represents the number of threads used on each processor. Analysing Fig. 1, in P_0 , is detailed the processor-level behavior and in P_1 how the computation is concurrently performed on nt threads. The domain decomposition is performed by P_0 dividing the transects into subsets as $\Delta_0, \Delta_1, \Delta_{np}$. The subsets are distributed to each processor P_p . Each processor P_p has its local particle data pD . For each processor P_p , the local particles dataset is divided into subsets sized as $\Delta_0, \Delta_1, \Delta_{nt}$ and assigned at each thread $t \in [0, nt]$. For each thread, T_t an algorithm is executed sequentially for each local thread transect data $tF_n \in pD_t$. P_0 cycle ends gathering alert indexes from each processor. The parallelization scheme (Fig. 1) enables the final user to choose any combination of the following execution models:

(i) Single run: the single process P_0 , calling the procedure *calculate alert index* solves sequentially the problem for all profiles of its domain D_t . (ii) Distributed memory run on np processes: each process $P_p, p \in [0, np]$, calling the procedure *calculate _alert index*, solves the problem for all transects of its sub-domain pD . (iii) Shared memory runs on nt threads: using the shared distribution paradigm, a subdomain of data tD is assigned at each thread of the multi-core environment. Each thread for $t \in [0, T]$, works on a sub-set tD , calling the procedure *calculate alert index*.

VI. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

To test the SAM performance, we set up a test-bed experiment using one computing node of the *purpleJeans*¹ an HPC system equipped with two Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5218 CPU @ 2.30 GHz (16 cores each). The number of transects considered was about 20K along the entire Campanian coast. However, this number can be further increased by reducing the distance between points in the shapefile. Furthermore, we consider different processors hosted on the same computing node, avoiding inter-node communications. Finally, we use the following configurations: (i) Baseline: we consider as Baseline the performance measured using only one process and only one thread. (ii) Distributed Memory (MPI approach): SAM has been tested using 1, 2, 4, and 8 MPI processes on the same computing node. (iii) Shared Memory (OpenMP approach): Considering only one MPI process, we used 1, 2, 4, and 8 threads. (iv) Distributed Memory and Shared Memory (MPI-OpenMP approach): for this evaluation, we run 1, 2, 4, and 8 MPI processes on the same computing node, varying the number of threads from 1 to 8. Figure 2 shows obtained runtime for the implementations above. For all subfigures, the number of MPI and OpenMP resources are indicated in the caption as follows, P is the number of MPI processes, and T displays the number of OpenMP processes considered for the computation. Figure 2a plots the behavior of the shared memory approach for SAM. It can be observed that the runtime decreases as the number of OpenMP

¹ <https://rcf.uniparthenope.it>

(a) OpenMP approach

(b) MPI approach

(c) MPI-OpenMP approach

Fig. 2: The execution time of the different approaches.

processes increases in comparison with an efficient sequential version (Baseline). Figure 2b plots the behavior

of the distributed memory approach. Again, it can be observed that the runtime decreases as the number of MPI processes increases. Finally, figure 2c shows the runtime for the hybrid approach based on OpenMP and MPI. In short, from Figure 2, we can conclude that the fastest implementation was the MPI-OpenMP approach with an improvement of ~ 24 times faster than the Baseline.

Fig. 3: a) Location of the 'Porto Scala' in the north area of the coast of Torre del Greco; b),c),d) Coastal damage surveyed on the promenade behind the breakwater the day after the storm surge.

VII. CASE STUDY

The stretch of the coast under examination is located in the municipality of Torre del Greco. It consists of a beach varying in width from 10 to 20 meters, protected by an artificial reef made up of natural blocks. In recent years, the succession of extreme weather events has created various coastal problems causing considerable damage to the city, particularly to the Porto Scala area close to the port (Fig. 3), which often suffered from coastal flooding like during the extreme storm of the October 2018 [22]. The succession of increasingly frequent high-intensity events is causing long-term damage and compromising the effectiveness of the current barriers. Mitigation is carried out concerning the environment, and the coastal system remains the primary objective for risk reduction in areas that are particularly exposed and increasingly vulnerable to climate change.

Fig. 4 illustrates a case study of the methodology presented in the paper. It focuses on the October 2018 storm, using wave height data from the Gulf of Torre del Greco during the night of the 27th-28th. The SAM system accurately detected these values and promptly triggered a coastal alert. Comparing postevent data with the system's response confirms its validity and coherence. Furthermore, the areas with the most severe damage during the storm had a high alert level from the SAM. It shows that the SAM can be useful for predicting and

mitigating potential coastal damage during severe weather and sea conditions.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we configured a set of forecasting tools using a high-performance computing system to manage and run a coastal flooding alert system on the beach transect of the area of interest. The results carried out by this research aim to mitigate the effects of global changes, giving the decision-makers, the scientists, and the engineers a novel, next-generation toolset for facing extreme weather events related management or emergency responses. The cloudnative/hierarchical heterogeneous high-performance computing enabled models for marine ingress/flooding forecasting. Merging the classical computational environmental science tool with the AI prediction models will significantly reduce social and economic costs of extreme weather events management responses, contributing to saving human life and production/business assets.

Fig. 4: Real case application: SAM results about the storm that hit the Gulf of Naples on October 27-28, 2018.

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